

About the possibility of a new Vertical Launch System for Space Vehicles via Reissner-Nordstrom Gravity

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Abstract

The radial geodesics of a neutral test macroscopic object in the spacetime geometry corresponding to a central massive and charged object (Reissner-Nordstrom Spacetime) is examined from the standpoint of the possibility of a new vertical launch system. It is shown that for radial geodesics located between $r = Q^2/(2Mc^2)$ and $r = Q^2/Mc^2$. M and Q being the mass and charge origin of the spacetime geometry, the gravitational force is repulsive, independently of the value of the gravitational constant G and the sign of the charge. From these results, at least in principle, it would be possible the construction of a Launch Platform for Space Vehicles and even conventional planes.

1 Introduction

In a recent paper [1] it was noticed the fact that from the standpoint of General Relativity (In the case studied, the Spacetime induced by the Reissner-Nordstrom Metric), all charged elementary particles and some composite

ones are Naked Singularities (NS) (i.e. $GM^2 - Q^2 < 0$), in contradiction with the Cosmic Censorship Principle. Even quarks which masses are yet poorly known (2-4 Mev for the Up and Down quarks) might also be NS. If at the atomic and molecular level gravitational forces are completely negligible in comparison with the electromagnetic ones that rule the dynamics, on the surface of the Earth, our daily lives evolve under its gravitational field. The question arises whether it could be possible to somehow build artificial macroscopic Naked Singularities which might be of practical use, principally, in the field of Spatial Travel.

A common feature of NS is the existence, as reported in [3] and [1], of a distance of null gravitational force located at a radial distance $Q^2/(Mc^2)$ from the singularity, being the force repulsive below this distance down to $Q^2/(2Mc^2)$ in which is maximal (Q and M being the charge and mass of the NS. Gaussian units will be used).

It is the main object of this work to explore the possibility of building a Launch Platform that could be used for giving an initial vertical boost to Space Rockets, and even Commercial Planes, sparing a good part of the combustible used in Space Missions

2 Radial Geodesics

In spherical coordinates $x^\alpha = (ct, r, \theta, \phi)$, the element of arch parametrized by proper time τ is

$$d\tau^2 = \left(1 - \frac{2GM}{c^2 r} + \frac{GQ^2}{c^4 r^2}\right) c^2 dt^2 - \left(1 - \frac{2GM}{c^2 r} + \frac{GQ^2}{c^4 r^2}\right)^{-1} dr^2 - r^2 d\theta^2 - r^2 \sin^2 \theta d\phi^2. \quad (1)$$

For the study of radial geodesics, a convenient start point is the Lagrangian [2]

$$\mathcal{L} = \frac{1}{2} \left[\left(1 - \frac{2GM}{c^2 r} + \frac{GQ^2}{c^4 r^2}\right) c^2 \dot{t}^2 - \left(1 - \frac{2GM}{c^2 r} + \frac{GQ^2}{c^4 r^2}\right)^{-1} \dot{r}^2 \right]. \quad (2)$$

(dot meaning derivative respect to proper time τ).

Together with the Euler-Lagrange equations

$$\frac{d}{d\tau} \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial \dot{x}^\alpha} - \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial x^\alpha} = 0. \quad (3)$$

For $x^0 = ct$, if we restrict to radial geodesics and since the coordinate time does not explicitly appears in the lagrangian, the corresponding canonical momentum of a test particle of mass m is a constant of the motion \tilde{m} , that can be interpreted as the momentum per unit mass:

$$u_0 = \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial \dot{t}} = \left(1 - \frac{2GM}{c^2 r} + \frac{GQ^2}{c^4 r^2}\right) u^0 = \tilde{m}. \quad (4)$$

If we drop the test particle from infinity on a radial trajectory beginning at rest, the constant \tilde{m} is simply unit. Then, from the last equation and (1):

$$u^0 = c \frac{dt}{d\tau} = \frac{c}{\left(1 - \frac{2GM}{c^2 r} + \frac{GQ^2}{c^4 r^2}\right)} \quad (5)$$

and

$$u^1 = \frac{dr}{d\tau} = \sqrt{\frac{2GM}{r} - \frac{GQ^2}{c^2 r^2}}. \quad (6)$$

The Christoffel symbols for the radial coordinate are:

$$\Gamma_{rr}^r = -\frac{\frac{GM}{c^2} - \frac{GQ^2}{c^2}}{r\left(r^2 - \frac{2GM}{c^2}r + \frac{GQ^2}{c^2}\right)}, \quad \Gamma_{tt}^r = \left(1 - \frac{2GM}{c^2 r} + \frac{GQ^2}{c^4 r^2}\right) \left(\frac{GM}{r^2} - \frac{GQ^2}{c^2 r^3}\right). \quad (7)$$

$$\Gamma_{tr}^r = \frac{\frac{GM}{c^2} - \frac{GQ^2}{c^2}}{r\left(r^2 - \frac{2GM}{c^2}r + \frac{GQ^2}{c^2}\right)}$$

From the precedent relations and the geodesics equations, the radial acceleration relative to the proper time is

$$\frac{d^2 r}{d\tau^2} = \frac{GM}{r^2} - \frac{GQ^2}{c^2 r^3}. \quad (8)$$

Irrespective of the value of the gravitational constant G , the right hand side is null for

$$r_{NF} = \frac{Q^2}{Mc^2}. \quad (9)$$

The well known expression determining the Event and Cauchy Horizons in RN spacetime is given by

$$r = \frac{1}{c^2} \left(GM \pm \sqrt{G(GM^2 - Q^2)} \right). \quad (10)$$

For $GM^2 - Q^2 > 0$ both kind of Horizons exist. The case $GM^2 - Q^2 = 0$ corresponds to a so called extremal black hole, while for $GM^2 - Q^2 < 0$ we have Naked Singularities.

There is a simply counting argument that rules out, for our purposes, all mentioned cases but the NS one. In the case of Black Holes from the condition

$$GM^2 - Q^2 \geq 0, \quad (11)$$

it follows that

$$GMc^2 - \frac{Q^2}{M}c^2 \geq 0$$

and therefore

$$\frac{GM}{c^2} - \frac{Q^2}{Mc^2} \geq 0.$$

For the Sun, the Schwarzschild radius is about 3 km. If we consider a Vertical Launching Site with a characteristic height about 50 meter (5000cm), then for $Q^2/Mc^2 = 5000$, in order of the last inequality to hold it would be necessary a mass of more than $6.73 \times 10^{31}g$, only two order of magnitude less than the mass of the Sun.

Strictly speaking, the momentum \tilde{m} per unit mass mentioned before cannot be 1 because any object on the Earth is bounded. However, the gravitational field of the Earth is extremely weak and the binding energy low.

By putting the null acceleration distance $r_{NF} = Q^2/(Mc^2)$ in (6) we find

$$u_r = c\sqrt{\frac{GM^2}{Q^2}}, \quad (12)$$

which only do not exceed the light velocity for $GM^2 \leq Q^2$. The above value is the maximum spatial part of the four-velocity for outgoing or ingoing radial geodesics.

The reader can easily verify that for $r = 1/2r_{NF}$, $u_r = 0$ while the acceleration is maximal (for r less than the former value u_r is imaginary). Turning now to the acceleration, from the previous expression (8) and for $r = Q^2/(2Mc^2)$:

$$\frac{d^2r}{d\tau^2} = -\frac{4GM^3c^4}{Q^4}, \quad (13)$$

which is the starting maximum repulsive acceleration.

The preceding relations are valid for a Naked Singularity in free space-time devoid of gravity. In our case the Dome harboring the NS should be placed at the Earth surface. Strictly speaking, in the presence of the gravitational field of the Earth the radial outgoing trajectories would no longer be geodesics equations obtained from the Affine Connections (7). However, the gravitational field of the Earth is sufficiently weak as to simply add both Earth's induced velocity and acceleration to the previous relations as a valid approximation.

Avoiding technical details which are out of the scope of this work, the Launch system might be something like an oversized Van der Graaff Generator consisting of a Dome shaped as a charged spherical shell with a flat platform on top for the Rocket or whatever Space Vehicle. The Dome should be covered by a dielectric shield to avoid ionic discharge by the air. These are technical challenges certainly not addressed in the present study.

3 Proper time vs Coordinate time

As we shall be dealing with a system of a size comparable to other human produced systems such as NASA Launch Platforms and Airports, but harboring relatively strong gravitational fields, it seems necessary to study such things as relations between stationary observers, coordinate time and proper time of eventual passengers.

We have been using radial four-velocities and four accelerations as if it were equivalent to normal velocities and accelerations, In the low velocity regime and relatively far from the singularity, the validity of such assumptions in our case should be analyzed.

For a static observer conveniently away from the launching area, the element of coordinate time versus proper time is given by

$$dt = \frac{d\tau}{\sqrt{\left(1 - \frac{2GM}{c^2 r} + \frac{GQ^2}{c^4 r^2}\right)}}. \quad (14)$$

Solving for the term under the square root equated to zero:

$$r = \frac{\sqrt{G}(\sqrt{GM} - \sqrt{GM^2 - Q^2})}{c^2}. \quad (15)$$

For $Q^2 > GM^2$ there is no real solution. For $r = Q^2/(Mc^2)$:

$$dt = \frac{d\tau}{\sqrt{1 - \frac{GM^2}{Q^2}}}. \quad (16)$$

Only real for NS. For $r = Q^2/(2Mc^2)$, it is straightforward to find that $dt = d\tau$, since this is the launch distance, it is a welcome result.

Let us now find the elapsed proper time from $\tau = 0$ to any radial distance below the corresponding to null acceleration which can be obtained by finding the primitive of the integral

$$\tau = \int \frac{dr}{\sqrt{\frac{2GM}{r} - \frac{GQ^2}{c^2r^2}}}. \quad (17)$$

Once integrated:

$$\tau = \frac{4Q^3}{3\sqrt{GM^2c^3}} - \frac{2(2Q^2 + Mc^2r)\sqrt{G(Q^2 - Mc^2r)}}{3GM^2c^3}. \quad (18)$$

The integral is well behaved and at $r = 0$, τ is also zero.

4 Final Results

According to the previous considerations, taking into account the presence of the Earth, equation (8) for the acceleration reads now:

$$\frac{d^2r}{d\tau^2} = \frac{GM_E}{(R+r)^2} + \frac{GM}{r^2} - \frac{GQ^2}{c^2r^3}, \quad (19)$$

where R and M_E are the mass and radius of the Earth. As for the velocity, there is a necessary correction adding a term in (6) given by $\sqrt{2ra}$ where $a = 980cm.s^{-2}$ is the constant acceleration at the surface of the Earth.

$$\frac{dr}{d\tau} = \sqrt{\frac{2GM}{r} - \frac{GQ^2}{c^2r^2}} - \sqrt{2ra}. \quad (20)$$

After giving account of the theoretical aspects we need now to give an estimation of the size and weight of an eventual Dome that could harbor the

NS (Something like a Dome shaped building finishing in a spherical shell of some 30 meters of radius).

According to the Equivalence Principle all test bodies move in the same way under a gravitational field. By test bodies it is mean that its masses should be negligible in comparison with the bodies harboring the gravitational fields (NS singularities in our case). on the other hand, by obvious reason, the mass of the Dome should be also negligible in comparison with the mass of the Earth. The mass of the Saturn 5 was of the order of 10^9 grams and the Earth mass is about 10^{27} grams. A compromise between both figures would be a Dome with a mass of the order of 10^{17} grams. Once having a choice for the mass, the amount of charge is related to the initial conditions for the vertical take off. We have assumed a launch platform located at about 30 meters above the singularity and some additional 30 meters from the Platform to the null force radial distance (See the caption of Figure 1 for the precise numbers). These values have been chosen so that the initial upwards acceleration will not exceed six times the Earth gravity that otherwise would be uncomfortable for the passengers. For these requirements a charge of about $10^{21}esu$ is required.

The following curves made for devices located in free space and at the surface of the Earth illustrate and resume these results.

Without the gravity of the Earth, with our data, the maximum velocity is $4594.43cm/s$ (165.4 km/hour). With the influence of Earth gravity, the velocity (eq (20)) is reduced to 45 km/hour.

In free space, far from the Earth, and starting from rest, the proper time required to attain the distance of null force (56.9 meter) according to (18) is 1.59 s. The coordinate time from (16) is almost the same (from the smallness of the dimensionless ratio $GM^2/Q^2 = 2.348 \times 10^{-14}$).¹

The figures correspond to devices set in free space and at the surface of the Earth. In all cases, the initial Boost and negative acceleration take place within the interval

¹Note that comparison of the quotient $Q^2/(GM^2)$ needed by the NS Dome with the corresponding to microscopic particles (the Proton for instance), we find for the Launching Dome a ratio 4.25765×10^{13} while for the proton, the ratio is 1.23572×10^{36} . Illustrative of how electromagnetic interactions dominates at the atomic scale.

$$(0.5, 1.0) \frac{Q^2}{Mc^2}.$$

A last remark is that all results do not depend on the sign of the charge (only on its square). In the not very plausible case of being made in great number and in order of not altering the net neutral charge of the Earth, the Launch Sites ought to be built in, far apart, pairs of opposite charge (a possible additional technical challenge).

5 Discussion

The following comments that are left aside, or rather, within my lack of an in-depth knowledge of both electrotechnics and physics of materials, are notwithstanding necessary to have a criterion about the feasibility of the project object of this study. In what has been said in the last section, there are numerical figures about the charge and total mass of the alleged Launching Site that might well be unattainable with current techniques. If we assume a spherical shell of 30 metres radius and 5 metres thickness, a mass of the order of $10^{14}kg$ would lead to a density about $2.1 \times 10^9 kg/m^3$. The density of nuclear matter is of the order of $10^{17}kg \times m^3$ (about the same in neutron stars). Relative to the charge density, for $Q = 10^{21}esu$ the volume charge density would be $2.1 \times 10^{10}esu/cm^3$. These are just raw numbers for electrical engineers that should ultimately judge the feasibility of the project.

Figure 1: Acceleration vs altitude including the contribution of the Earth Gravitational Field. By comparison with the following Figure, it is clearly seen how the Earth increases the acceleration towards the Earth (positive values). Charge $Q = 3.0342 \times 10^{21} esu$, Mass $M = 18 \times 10^{17} g$. The Launch radial distance is at $1/2r_{NF} = 2845cm$. The same values in the other figures

Figure 2: Acceleration in Free Space other than the NS

Figure 3: Velocity curve vs distance without the inclusion of the Earth Gravitational Field. The maximum velocity is located at $Q^2/(Mc^2)$

Figure 4: Velocity curve vs altitude including the Earth field. In this case the action of the Earth produce a displacement of the maximum velocity to a much lower value and a fast decrease of the velocity (the velocity drops to zero at some 92 meters)

References

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